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ABSTRACT BOOK

Free Papers

Treatment of open extruded fracture neck of the talus using the combined method of external fixation modified for dynamic ankle joint fixation and Kirschner wires - case report

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Abstract

Introduction: Open extruded fracture of the talus is present in 2% of talar fractures. Because of numerous complications (infection, nonunions, arthritis), it represents a great challenge for the surgeon. The most commonly used method of treatment is reimplantation of the talus and osteosynthesis.

Case presentation: A 19-year-old patient suffered an open extruded fracture of the talus type Hawkins II after falling from a height. The emergency operative technique that we performed was debridement of the wound, reimplantation of the talus bone, osteosynthesis with external fixation modified for dynamic external fixation of the ankle joint (Mitkovic-type), and two Kirschner wires. Reposition of fragments we controlled with C-Arm fluoroscopy. The patient was prescribed 14 days antibiotic therapy (cephalosporin, aminoglycoside, mebendazole) and thromboembolic prophylaxis for 35 days. After 6 weeks we allowed movements in the ankle joint with physical therapy. Gradual weight-bearing in the injured leg was allowed after 8 weeks. The osteosynthetic material was removed after 18 weeks, and the treatment continued with physical therapy with a full weight bearing on the leg after 6 months. X-ray follow-up of the talus was done for 2 months until the 24th month postoperatively. An excellent result was obtained with a healed talus and minimal restriction of dorsiflexion of the foot.

Conclusion: Treatment of this injury represents a huge challenge for the surgeon. External fixation can be chosen as a treatment method for an open luxation fracture of the talus.

Keywords: case report, open extruded talar fracture, external fixation, Kirschner wires.